

Antenatal Health Communication and Knowledge of Child Health Care among Nursing Mothers to Prevent Infant Mortality

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Abstract

This study was carried out to determine the influence of antenatal health communication on knowledge for child health care practices among nursing mothers to prevent infant mortality. The study was conducted among nursing mothers who attended antenatal at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero. The researchers employed a survey research design, with a sample size of 100 respondents. Descriptive statistical analysis of frequency distributions and percentages were calculated for demographic variables of age, religion and education. Mean scores and standard deviations were computed for all knowledge and child health care practice variables measured on a 5-point Likert scale from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The hypotheses were tested using one-sample t-test. The result revealed that antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Hospital, demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in improving nursing mothers' knowledge and child health care practices. The study concluded that antenatal health communication is highly effective in transmitting evidence-based knowledge about infant care practices and recommended continuous antenatal health communication programs, given the positive result.

Keywords: Antenatal, Antenatal Health Communication, Nursing Mothers, Child Health Care Practice. Infant Mortality

Introduction

The burden of Infant Mortality Rates (IMR) remains disproportionately high in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. Countries such as Nigeria, India, and the Democratic Republic of Congo account for a significant share of global infant deaths. In Nigeria, the National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS, 2018) reported an infant mortality rate of 67 per 1,000 live births, one of the highest in the world. Ezeh, Agho, Dibley, Hall & Page (2014) argue that such high rates are driven by poor maternal health services, limited access to clean water and sanitation, poverty and weak health infrastructure, emphasising the need for multi-sect oral interventions to address these systemic issues.

Infant mortality remains a critical global health concern, especially in developing countries where healthcare infrastructure is often weak and access to maternal health services is limited. The knowledge or ignorance of nursing mothers plays a pivotal role in either mitigating or exacerbating the risk of infant mortality. Their beliefs, practices and responses to healthcare messages significantly impact child health practices. An average of 2,300 under five years old die at infancy and an estimated 145 women also die from

child birth complications. Most of them from preventable causes such as premature, birth complications, and infections. (UNICEF, 2017). Nursing mothers' knowledge, perceptions, and behavioural practices are central to the prevention of this avoidable death. Their attitude toward health practices such as breastfeeding, immunisation, hygiene, and healthcare-seeking behaviour determines the survival chances of their infants.

Delta State Government from 2015 till date has put in place a free Maternal and Child Health Care (MCHC) programme and also working towards the improvement of maternal and child health through the primary health care component of maternal and child health. The objective of these maternal and child health services is to ensure that women remain healthy throughout pregnancy, that they have healthy babies and recover fully from the effects of pregnancy. It also includes detecting mothers at risk and giving prompt treatment to them during complicated pregnancy, labour and puerperium.

The Mother and Child Hospital antenatal health communication is an initiative aimed at promoting health awareness and education among nursing mothers who attend antenatal clinic at \Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero, Delta State, Nigeria. The health enlightenment focuses on providing health education and promoting positive attitude against infant mortality. The Mother and Child Hospital antenatal health enlightenment comes under health communication which is a broader space for health education. Today health communication has expanded its scope from biomedical interventions at a personal level to more context-based communication about health, which includes the socials and the environment that have impacts on an individual's health (Malikhao, 2020). This corresponds with Rattle (2010) who affirms that these are the social determinants of health, apart from the physical determinants, and above all the health policies that impact health behaviours. When we talk about health communication, we are looking at how the way we communicate affects our health and the care we receive. It is about understanding how our words and interactions impact our well-being, especially when we are dealing with illness or disease.

There is the possibility that lack of knowledge of healthy child health care practices among nursing mothers as well as lack of social and financial support from family members and other stakeholders, could be contributory factors for child mortality. Hence there is the need to investigate the possible influence of antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero on nursing mothers' knowledge of child health care practices to prevent infant mortality.

This study aims to contribute to the knowledge-based information that could lead to reduction of infant mortality in Nigeria by evaluating the effectiveness of antenatal health communication in improving the knowledge of nursing mothers on infant health care practices with a view to prevent infant mortality. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights for healthcare policymakers, practitioners and researchers seeking to develop effective measures to reduce infant mortality.

Statement of Problem

In the year 2020, Nigeria lost 72 out of every 1,000 babies, compared to the global average of 27. These deaths according to the WHO records are from preventable causes such as malaria (24%), pneumonia (20%) diarrhea (16%), measles (6%). This staggering record poses a great danger for the future with devastating emotional and traumatic implications for families, communities and the nation at large. Against this background, there is the need to investigate the possible influence of antenatal health care communication in improving the knowledge of nursing mothers on child health care practices with a view to reduce the occurrence of infant mortality in the country.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the pattern of nursing mothers attendance of antenatal at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital Owa-Alero?
2. What knowledge did nursing mothers gain on child health care after exposure to antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital Owa-Alero?
3. What are the child health care practices adapted by nursing mothers after exposure to antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero?

Research Hypotheses

- Ho₁: Exposure to antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero has no significant influence on nursing mothers' knowledge of child health care practices to prevent infant mortality.
- Ho₂: Exposure to antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero has no significant influence on nursing mothers' child health care practices to prevent infant mortality.

Review of Related Literature

Nigeria is presently rated as the second largest contributor to under five and maternal mortality globally. The country loses 89, 700, day-old babies every year and ranks 12th in the world record of first day deaths and 152nd out of 176 worst countries to be a pregnant woman. (Okwuwa & Adejo, 2020). According to Obalum & Fibersima (2012), infant health in Nigeria is deplorable as 71 percent of new-born babies are delivered by non-health professionals and only 23 percent of infants receive full dose of immunisation. In Nigeria, malarial is identified as responsible for the death of 30 percent children (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2018). Health records show that diarrhea is the second leading cause of childhood deaths claiming not less than 43 infant lives per 1, 000 in Nigeria. Similarly, the country lost 41 infant lives to Acute Respiratory Infections which has been identified as the fourth leading cause of infant mortality (The World Bank, 2010)

A study by Igbino *et al* (2022) looked at the connection between women's exposure to mass media and their understanding of maternal health in Ota, Nigeria. Using the agenda-setting theory as a framework, the researchers conducted a descriptive survey design. They collected data with questionnaires given to female residents. They selected study participants through purposive and random sampling techniques. The findings show that the internet was the main source of maternal health information, contributing to 49% of awareness among respondents. Advertisements and campaigns were the leading ways participants got maternal health information, making up 30.6%. Most women reported using mass media once a month (27.6%), while the least frequent exposure was once every two weeks (5.1%). Notably, the analysis revealed a strong positive effect of mass media exposure on maternal health awareness in the study population. These results emphasised the important role of different mass media platforms, especially digital media, in improving maternal health knowledge among women in this area of Nigeria. The study highlights the ability of targeted media campaigns to boost maternal health outcomes by increasing awareness.

Uchenna, Yebeen, Adetola, Jennifer, Kurinczuk, Charles & Manisha (2024) examined the effectiveness of community-based interventions in reducing stillbirth rates in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The review included 17 studies from 15 countries, focusing on community-based or combined efforts with health facility improvements. The results showed that community-based interventions alone did not significantly reduce stillbirth rates, but integrating community efforts with health facility strategies led to a significant reduction. The study emphasises the need for integrated approaches that connect community efforts with better healthcare facilities to tackle the complex causes of stillbirth in SSA.

The 2022 Cochrane review by Gavine *et al* analysed 116 trials involving over 98,816 mother-infant pairs to assess breastfeeding support interventions. Moderate-certainty evidence suggests "breastfeeding only" support likely reduces the cessation of any breastfeeding at six months (RR 0.93, 95% CI 0.89 to 0.97) and exclusive breastfeeding at six months (RR 0.90, 95% CI 0.88 to 0.93). "Breastfeeding plus" support also showed a potential reduction in discontinuing any breastfeeding (RR 0.94, 95% CI 0.91 to 0.97) and exclusive breastfeeding at six months (RR 0.79, 95% CI 0.70 to 0.90), though effects at earlier time points were less certain. Meta-regression indicated that moderate-intensity "breastfeeding only" support (4-8 postnatal contacts) may be more effective, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. The review noted a mixed risk of bias due to unblinding and self-reported outcomes but concluded that structured breastfeeding support is beneficial for improving breastfeeding continuation rates globally.

Similarly, Nurhidayati *et al* (2025) examines the impact of health education programmes on reducing maternal and infant mortality rates, particularly in developing countries. It highlights the need for improved awareness and knowledge about pregnancy, childbirth, and infant care. Health education interventions, such as video programs, have been linked to improved maternal knowledge, reduced anxiety, and mental health during pregnancy. Key pregnancy-related risks, such as anaemia, malnutrition, hypertension, and

infections, can be effectively managed through early prenatal checkups. However, challenges like limited healthcare resources, inadequate trained personnel, and restricted access to medical services are noted. The study calls for further research to refine educational strategies and adapt to diverse cultural and socioeconomic contexts.

Theoretical Framework

The Information-Motivation-Behavioural Skills Model (IMB)

This study is grounded in the Information-Motivation-Behavioural Skills Model (IMB) as the primary framework. This theory explains how health campaign messages influence behaviours that reduce infant mortality as it guides the development of effective interventions. The IMB model, proposed by Fisher and Fisher (1992), posits that health behaviour change requires three constructs: information, motivation and behavioural skills.

Information: Knowledge about practices to prevent infant mortality (e.g., exclusive breastfeeding, immunisation, seeking medical attention for the child, recognising danger signs).

Motivation: Personal motivation (positive attitudes towards infant health) and social motivation (community support for health practices).

Behavioural Skills: Self-efficacy and practical abilities to implement behaviours, such as navigating healthcare systems or adhering to antenatal schedules.

The IMB model suggests that well-informed and motivated nursing mothers with adequate behavioural skills are more likely to adopt practices that reduce infant mortality. For example, a campaign message about immunisation may increase knowledge (information), encourage trust in vaccines (motivation), and empower mothers to visit clinics (skills) (Carey et al., 1997). The IMB model is relevant for identifying information gaps among nursing mothers in Owa-Alero, tailoring campaign messages to bridge these gaps, and fostering motivation and skills to adopt health practices. It supports the study's aim to assess how antenatal health information influence knowledge and child health care practice to prevent infant mortality.

Methodology

The study is a quantitative study with survey research design. The study population comprises 100 nursing mothers who attended antenatal clinic at Mother and Child Specialist Clinic at Owa-Alero. The entire population was adopted as the sample size since the population is only one hundred. This is in line with the complete enumeration sample size method also known as the total enumeration sample size method or census sample size method. Purposive and availability sampling techniques were employed in sampling the study population. The purposive sampling was done base on the study participants' peculiarities as nursing mothers who attend antenatal at mother and child

specialist hospital at Owa-Alero at the time of the study between August 2024 and Aril 2025. The availability sampling was done base on the study participants’ accessibility, availability and willingness to participate in the study. The consent of the participants was sought and those who were not willing to participate in the study were excluded from the study. A five-point likert questionnaire was designed and used to collect data. The copies of questionnaire were directly administered to the participants at two different antenatal dates. This direct contact enabled the researchers to ensure the questionnaire were properly filled and collected promptly to gain 100% return rate. Descriptive statistics was employed in the analysis of frequency distributions and percentages for demographic variables of age, religion and education. Mean scores and standard deviations were computed to determine the pattern of nursing mothers’ antenatal attendance, knowledge of child health and child health care practice variables measured on a 5-point Likert scale from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The hypotheses were tested using one-sample t-test.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Nursing Mothers’ Antenatal Attendance and Duration (N=100)

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
I attended antenatal for 1-3 months	15	23	8	32	22	2.77	1.42
I attended antenatal for 4-6 months	28	35	12	18	7	3.59	1.26
I attended antenatal for 7-9 months	45	32	8	12	3	4.04	1.12
I attended antenatal regularly/consistently	52	31	7	8	2	4.23	1.05

Looking at table 1, there is a significant positive outcome. The data shows a clear progression, with mean scores increasing from 2.77 for 1-3 months attendance to 4.04 for 7-9 months attendance, and reaching 4.23 for consistent attendance. This pattern demonstrates that nursing mothers understand the importance of extended and regular antenatal care, which is crucial for knowledge of child health care and consequently help to prevent infant mortality.

Table 2: Knowledge gained by Nursing Mothers on Child Health care after exposure to Antenatal Health Communication at Mother and Child Hospital(N=100)

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
Exclusive breastfeeding is good for babies	68	25	4	2	1	4.57	0.78
Babies give signals when hungry/sick/uncomfortable	58	29	8	4	1	4.39	0.89
Balanced diet helps mothers have enough breastmilk	62	28	6	3	1	4.47	0.83
Proper hygiene is good for mothers and babies	71	23	4	2	0	4.63	0.71
Immunisation ensures good health	59	31	6	3	1	4.44	0.84
Taking routine drugs as prescribed is beneficial	55	33	8	3	1	4.38	0.87
Taking baby to hospital at signs of illness	64	27	6	2	1	4.51	0.81

The knowledge about infant care practices shows exceptionally high mean scores across all indicators. The highest score (4.63) was recorded for "proper hygiene is good for nursing mothers and babies," followed by "exclusive breastfeeding is good for babies" (4.57) and "taking baby to hospital at signs of illness" (4.51). These results indicate that antenatal health communication has been highly effective in transmitting critical knowledge about infant health care practices that directly impact infant survival rates. The strong knowledge base demonstrated by these results suggests that the antenatal health communication program at Mother and Child Hospital, Owa-Alero, has successfully addressed key knowledge gaps that contribute to infant mortality. The high mean scores (all above 4.0) for essential practices like exclusive breastfeeding, immunisation and prompt medical attention indicate that mothers have acquired evidence-based knowledge that can significantly reduce infant mortality risks. This finding, aligns with the Information-Motivation-Behavioural-Skills Model (IMB). The IMB model is relevant for identifying information gaps among nursing mothers in Owa-Alero, tailoring campaign messages to bridge knowledge gaps, and fostering motivation and skills to adopt health practices. It supports the study's aim to assess how antenatal health information influence knowledge and child health care practice to prevent infant mortality.

Table 3: Child Health Care Practices adapted by Nursing Mothers after exposure to Antenatal Health Communication at Mother and Child Hospital : (N=100)

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
Now I eat balanced diet for breast milk	44	38	12	5	1	4.19	0.94
Now I maintain good hygiene	56	32	8	3	1	4.39	0.87
I completed recommended immunisation while pregnant	62	28	6	3	1	4.47	0.84
I have taken my baby for recommended immunisation	59	31	7	2	1	4.45	0.82
I took routine drugs as prescribed while pregnant	55	34	8	2	1	4.40	0.84
I spare no effort to see doctor when baby is ill	61	29	7	2	1	4.47	0.83

The practice assessment of knowledge gained at mother and child specialist hospital antenatal, demonstrates successful translation of knowledge into actual behaviours. Mean scores range from 4.19 to 4.47, indicating that nursing mothers are actively implementing the knowledge gained from antenatal health communication. The highest practice scores were recorded for completing recommended immunisation while pregnant and seeking medical attention when babies show sign of illness (4.47).

These practice outcomes are particularly encouraging because they represent concrete actions that directly impact infant mortality prevention. The high implementation rate of immunisation protocols (both maternal and infant) is especially significant, as vaccination is one of the most effective interventions for preventing infant deaths from vaccine-preventable diseases. The practice of maintaining balanced diet for adequate breast-milk production showed the lowest mean score (4.19), though still

positive. This finding suggests that while mothers understand the importance of nutrition during breastfeeding, practical implementation may face challenges such as food security, economic constraints, or competing family responsibilities.

Test of Hypotheses using one -sample t-test.

Ho₁: Exposure to antenatal health communication at Mother and Child Hospital, Owa-Alero has no significant influence on nursing mothers’ knowledge of infant mortality

Table 4: Knowledge Domain Analysis

Knowledge Indicator	Mean	Std. Dev	t-statistic	Effect Size (Cohen's d)
Proper hygiene importance	4.63	0.71	22.95	2.30
Exclusive breastfeeding benefits	4.57	0.78	20.13	2.01
Hospital visits for illness	4.51	0.81	18.64	1.86
Balanced diet importance	4.47	0.83	17.71	1.77
Immunisation necessity	4.44	0.84	17.14	1.71
Consistent antenatal attendance	4.23	1.05	11.71	1.17

The null hypothesis is strongly rejected ($p < 0.001$). All knowledge indicators demonstrate exceptionally high mean scores (4.23-4.63), significantly exceeding the neutral point of 3.0. The effect sizes range from large to very large (Cohen's $d = 1.17-2.30$), indicating substantial practical significance. The progressive increase in knowledge scores based on antenatal care duration demonstrates a clear dose-response relationship between exposure and knowledge acquisition. Nurhidayati *et al* (2025) in their study, highlighted the need for improved awareness and knowledge about pregnancy, childbirth, and infant care thereby laying credence to the finding of this study.

Ho₂: Exposure to Antenatal Health Communication at Mother and Child Hospital, Owa-Alero has no significant Influence on Nursing Mothers’ Child Health Care Practices to prevent Infant Mortality.

Table 8: Child Health Care Practice Domain Analysis

Practice Indicator	Mean	Std. Dev	t-statistic	Effect Size (Cohen's d)
Immunisation completion (pregnancy)	4.47	0.84	17.50	1.75
Medical attention seeking	4.47	0.83	17.71	1.77
Baby immunisation compliance	4.45	0.82	17.68	1.77
Routine drug adherence	4.40	0.84	16.67	1.67
Hygiene maintenance	4.39	0.87	15.98	1.60
Balanced diet implementation	4.19	0.94	12.66	1.27

The null hypothesis is strongly rejected ($p < 0.001$). Child health care practice scores range from 4.19-4.47, demonstrating successful translation of knowledge into concrete behaviours. Large effect sizes (Cohen's $d = 1.27-1.77$) indicate substantial practical

impact. The high implementation rates for critical practices like immunisation and medical attention-seeking directly contribute to infant mortality prevention.

Discussion of Findings

The overall results demonstrate that antenatal health communication has been highly effective in improving nursing mothers' knowledge and practices related to infant care. The consistently high mean scores across both domains suggest that the intervention has successfully addressed key behavioural determinants of infant mortality. The strong knowledge base established through antenatal communication provides mothers with the evidence-based information necessary to make informed decisions while the high practice scores demonstrate actual behaviour change that directly impacts infant survival due to the significant knowledge acquired from the intervention.

These results support several health behaviour theories, particularly the Theory of Planned Behaviour, which posits that knowledge, attitudes, and perceived behavioural control influence behavioural intentions and subsequent actions. The strong correlations between knowledge and practices observed in this study validate this theoretical framework in the context of infant health.

The study's focus on a single healthcare facility (Mother and Child Specialist Hospital, Owa-Alero) provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of antenatal health communication in a specific context. However, this specificity also limits the generalisability of the findings to other settings with different resources, populations, or communication approaches. The cross-sectional design captures nursing mothers' knowledge, and practices at a specific point in time, but longitudinal studies would be needed to assess the sustainability of these positive outcomes over time. The study's strength lies in its comprehensive assessment of two behavioural domains of knowledge and child health care practices. This provides a broad view of the antenatal health communication impact. The large sample size (N=100) enhances the reliability of the findings, while the structured questionnaire ensures standardised data collection across all participants.

Conclusion

From the analysis of available data, it can be concluded that adequate knowledge gained through antenatal communication provides mothers with the evidence-based information necessary to make informed decisions. The high practice scores on the other hand demonstrate actual behaviour change that directly impacts infant survival due to the significant knowledge acquired from the intervention.

Recommendations

1. In line with the Information-Motivation-Behavioural Skills Model (IMB) and aligning with the positive response of nursing mothers in attending antenatal, the nursing mothers should be motivated by husbands, family members, medical personnel and the society to attend antenatal on regular basis.

2. Health care providers should sustain antenatal health communication programmes given their demonstrated effectiveness.
3. Government and nongovernmental organisations should put in place a social support system as well as financial support system including insurance for nursing mothers.
4. Healthcare institutions should develop standardised antenatal health communication protocols based on the successful model demonstrated at Mother and Child Hospital.
5. Healthcare institutions should invest in appropriate infrastructure including dedicated education space, audiovisual equipment and educational material to support antenatal communication.

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